

English teachers' practices and beliefs towards instructional media in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT

Teachers' practices and beliefs about instructional media are crucial in teaching English, as they can motivate students' enthusiasm if teachers use them engagingly. Despite their importance, teachers' practices and beliefs regarding instructional media in Islamic secondary schools in Indonesia have received less attention. The purpose of this qualitative study was to discover how teachers used instructional media and their beliefs towards employing it to teach English. We gathered information from two female English teachers at selected Islamic junior high schools in Aceh, Indonesia through observations and interviews. The results revealed that teachers utilized photos, whiteboards, overhead projectors, and flashcards to teach English. In their English foreign language classrooms, they used instructional media to facilitate students' learning by explaining the materials, and giving exercises. Teachers believed that instructional media could help boost students' interest, facilitate the learning process, and promote the achievement of teaching and learning objectives. They specified that curriculum and topic lessons are essential factors to consider when selecting instructional media for teaching English. They alleged that students' feedback, participation in seminars or workshops, self-discovery, and new curricula could all have an impact on their beliefs. Future research should look into potentially more comprehensive accounts of teachers' practices and beliefs about instructional media in varied secondary school contexts as well as how engaged students in more interactive classroom activities.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In English as a foreign language (EFL) teaching, there is an increasing interest in developing instructional media use for teachers. The reason is simple, instructional media are believed to play a significant role in building students learning enthusiasm and motivation [1], [2]. Thus, nowadays, it seems necessary to transform dull EFL classrooms focused exclusively on traditional learning sources into lively and vibrant EFL classrooms with diverse learning inspiration [3]. Various instructional media are thus interchangeably used and introduced to students [4]. Hence, teachers must be capable of using suitable instructional media in different EFL classroom contexts.

Sukmahidayanti [5] argued that earlier studies found that many teachers have problems in implementing instructional media because they believe using them is costly. Furthermore, Utami [4] has done comparable studies on teachers' views and practices in EFL classrooms. Teachers' beliefs also influence teachers' success because they give direction for implementing a reform based on their professional practices, principles and experiences during the teaching process [6]. The teachers' belief also an influence their use of various classroom strategies and media [4].

In discussing teachers' beliefs, the literature noted that they are ideas from teachers themselves about how teaching should be done, which includes core and peripheral beliefs [7]. Therefore, belief is a critical component in the educational process' growth and development in the classrooms [8]. It helps teachers provide direction on how to use effective and professional responsibility in their teaching practices [9]. Teachers' beliefs shape their perceptions of whether or not they need to enhance their teaching and how they will cope with challenges in implementing their teaching strategies [10]. It means that teachers are willing to learn more about their students, the material being taught, and the methods they might use to improve their teaching [11]. Teachers integrate their beliefs when designing a plan that includes media, approach, and material.

According to Harmer [12], teachers can utilize several types of instructional media to organize instructional activities and facilitate students in achieving instructional goals. Firstly, it is the students themselves; the students are "the classroom's most valuable resource" [12]. Secondly, realia or outside-the-classroom objects and teaching props are used for teaching and learning purpose [13]. They can be used to begin a lesson or explain a concept. Next, pictures or graphic materials used by teachers to interact with their students include drawings, cards, charts, graphs, posters, and cartoons. In addition to this, Harmer [12] explained that pictures could be used in a variety of ways, such as drilling, communication, comprehension, decoration, prediction, and discussion.

The other common media type are course books and boards [13], [14]. The coursebook contains printed content or verbal information that the teachers can use as a basic instruction guide. In contrast, boards include chalkboards, blackboards, whiteboards, and interactive whiteboards. Another instructional media type is overhead projectors that enable students to view contents in transparent projection in front of the class. Flipchart consists of many sheets of paper that are used to write some key remarks during group discussions. Finally, there is computer-assisted presentation technology. This media incorporates both audio and visual elements. Teachers may communicate significantly more knowledge to students by using computer-based presentation technology, also known as multimedia presentation [15]. Teacher beliefs are judgments we make about ourselves, others, and the world, and they are most commonly classified into two major views: knowledge transfer and reflective practice/learning facilitation [16]. They are subjective perceptions based on observation of an actual sense of reality [17]. Furthermore, belief is essential in the teaching process since it is formed by academic optimism and evolves into personal judgment [18]. Beliefs emerge gradually but steadily over time.

Regarding teachers' beliefs, Chamorro and Rey [19] clarify that teachers' actions and decisions in the classroom were influenced by their views. Teachers' beliefs can be divided into five groups, all interconnected: attitudes about students and learning, teaching beliefs, curricular perspectives, learning to teach beliefs, and beliefs about oneself and the nature of teaching [20]–[21]. According to Donnell and Gettinger [22], teachers' acceptability and attitudes about school change are influenced by their self-efficacy and professional development. They serve as a filter through which teachers explain new knowledge and greatly impact on how they educate. What teachers do in the classroom does not always reflect their ideas. Regardless, the impact on their teaching decisions and how they learn during their language teaching program is significant. Then, teachers may favor a specific way because it fits their personality [23].

Similarly, Davies *et al.* [24] noted that the teachers' beliefs, characteristics and school contexts resulting the different type of teacher instructional practices applied in the classroom atmosphere. During those experiences, teachers participate in various self-construction activities and enrichments, creating an insightful teaching experience with their students [25]. They assert that the assimilation of culture helped shape these perspectives. Mansour [26] divides experiences into two categories: formal and informal. The formal experience is represented by the official teaching received by teachers at schools or universities. Meanwhile, the informal experience of teachers is shown by their daily life interactions, which may modify, help, contest, or adapt their beliefs and responsiveness.

Kissau *et al.* [27] are among the researchers who have found a link between teachers' beliefs and their instructional techniques. They looked at 222 teachers' preexisting conceptions about teaching and found that they differed. The findings revealed that teachers with ten years of classroom experience had strong opinions on the relevance of grammar instruction. Meanwhile, teachers with less experience focused more on syntactical procedures, which stifled the development of verbal skills. Yook [28] further found that teachers have strong opinions about teaching and learning. They serve as knowledge transmitters, disseminators, and filters for first-hand information, ensuring that established beliefs are confirmed rather than challenged. Thus,

teacher education and professional learning mechanism during those processes should not restrict teachers from altering their beliefs if these shifts are indispensable for their professional growth [29]. Instead, teacher education programs should understand how teachers form opinions and how these ideas influence their teaching principles and practices [30].

To summarize, previous research has revealed that training courses, learning experiences, professional development, teaching experiences, and teaching styles all influence teachers' beliefs. Teachers rely on their prior views to teach and learn, and these beliefs impact what they learn and how they learn during their teacher education. In addition, changes in the learning environment have an impact on teachers' identities and teaching methods as well [31]. Consequently, what teachers understand about specific changes in English language education and what they believe about those changes is strongly linked.

However, there is a dearth of research on how English teachers, especially those in Aceh, Indonesia, use instructional media in their classrooms. One of the influential factors appears to be teachers' beliefs [32], yet little is known about their beliefs and practices on this matter. Moreover, more research has yet to explore their views on this matter. English is regarded as a foreign language in Indonesia. To acquire a better understanding of the specific developments in English language education, it is necessary to investigate instructors' attitudes toward teaching a foreign language. Understanding teachers' views help shape students' learning by providing evidence for their thinking, as well as classroom practices, instructional styles, and professional development ideas [33]. Hence, this research specifically examined Acehese teachers' beliefs toward instructional media and its technology in the classrooms. The questions to be answered are: i) how do English teachers in Aceh use instructional media to teach in their classrooms; and ii) what are their beliefs on utilizing instructional media to teach in their classrooms.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. Design

This study used qualitative research design with phenomenology approach as it seeks to find answers on how English teachers in Aceh use instructional media to teach in their classrooms as well as their beliefs about using instructional media to teach in their classrooms. In this case, the qualitative research is useful to provide a detailed explanation of the unique phenomena and elaborate on the participants' experiences and views or voices of the participants.

2.2. Participants

The research participants were selected through a purposive sampling technique [34]. To ensure the participants met the criteria we set, we conducted a pilot study by interviewing the prospective participants using the snowball sampling method and preliminary observations by asking them to send video clips of them using instructional media in English language teaching in classrooms. We looked for participants who had at least four years' experience teaching English at Islamic secondary schools across Aceh, and had graduated from the Department of English Language Education of the two most prestigious public universities in Aceh; Universitas Syiah Kuala and Universitas Islam Negeri Ar-Raniry Banda Aceh. Participants should have used instructional media with students in the classrooms and be willing to participate in this study. Subsequently, we purposively selected six Islamic junior high school teachers across Aceh willing to participate in this study. As a result, they are all female teachers from the Islamic Junior High School No. 2 Banda Aceh, Islamic Junior High School No. 7 Banda Aceh, Junior High School No.2 Aceh Besar, Junior High School 4 South Aceh, Junior High School 11, Nagan Raya, and Private Junior High School in West. The teachers participating in this study were between 26 and 32 years old.

2.3. Instruments

2.3.1. The observation

To collect the data, two instruments were employed; they were participant observations and in-depth interviews. For the first research question, participant observation technique was used to create an observation sheet to collect data on how teachers use instructional media when teaching English in the classroom. Here, we observed and recorded the classroom condition, the number of students in each class, the classroom facilities, and the steps or process of teaching done by each teacher from beginning to end by paying special attention to the media they used. In terms of data collections through observations, each teacher was observed in two-class meeting sessions at their respective schools to observe the instructional media they utilized in teaching.

2.3.2. The interviews

For the second research question, in addition to the participant observations, we developed some main questions for the in-depth interviews to inquire about the teachers' beliefs, practices, and reflections on the use of instructional media in their classrooms. Probing questions were asked to further elicit more information about their responses. Six teachers from secondary Islamic junior high schools across Aceh were interviewed. Each participant was interviewed by phone for approximately 45 to 60 minutes. Meanwhile, in relation to data collection from interviews, each teacher was questioned further about their perspectives, experiences and reflections on using instructional media to teach English in their classes. The interviews were conducted in Indonesian and English. They were recorded while interviews were taking place and the recordings were later transcribed.

2.4. Data analysis

Both data from the observations and interviews were analyzed using Creswell's procedures [41], which included preparing and organizing the raw data ranging from the notes in the observation sheets and interview transcripts, coding and analyzing the data, interpreting the significance of themes. In the following subsections, the findings from the observations and interviews are presented concurrently to supplement the findings for each research question. When analyzing the data, we qualitatively coded the English teacher from Islamic Junior High School No. 2 as TC1, the English teacher from Islamic Junior High School No. 7 as TC2, the English teacher from Junior High School No. 2 Aceh Besar as TC3, the English teacher from Junior High School 4 South Aceh as TC4, the English teacher from Junior High School 11 Nagan Raya as TC5, and the English teacher from Islamic Private Junior High School in West Aceh as TC6.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

3.1.1. Using instructional media to teach English in the classroom

Based on our observation, in the opening activity of the class, TC1 and TC2 directly presented the instructional media in the classroom. For instance, TC1 used illustrations, flashcards, and a whiteboard to teach about the past tense. TC1 informed that her choice of instructional media depended on the topics, as extracted from the interviews in E1:

E1: *"I use instructional media depending on the topic that I teach. Sometimes I use a laptop or slides when teaching 'text-types'. But when I teach 'grammar', using flashcards or visuals is easier, so it depends."* (TC1).

In the first observation, TC1 spent about 20 minutes explaining the use of past tense by using pictures of human activities. She instructed the students to look at the pictures depicting past tense actions, such as regular and irregular verbs of "purchase" to "bought", "play" to "played", and "is" to "was". She made use of the whiteboard to deliver and present more information and examples concerning the past tense to her students as the medium.

In the next meeting, which was still about the topic of using "past tense", TC1 continued to use the whiteboard and flashcards to teach her students. When students became confused, TC1 used the pictures to re-explain the simple past tense and added more examples on the whiteboard. Then, she used flashcards to help her students learn about the simple past tense. For example, the phrases "yesterday" and "last night" were put on two flashcards, one of which was prepared by TC1. She used flashcards to teach the students about time signals (yesterday and last night).

On the other hand, TC2 was more dynamic in using a variety of media. In the first observation, she used visuals to teach noun phrases in descriptive texts. She prepared the media and showed it to her class. In the second observation, she continued to teach noun phrases in descriptive texts, but this time she showed pictures to her students using a liquid crystal display (LCD) projector and her laptop. She displayed media in the classroom by setting up an LCD projector and connecting it to her laptop for her teaching and learning process.

Furthermore, TC2 used pictures to teach noun phrases in the first observation. She reviewed the material and gave examples of using pictures to build a noun phrase. For instance, TC2 taught her students about adjectives and showed them how to make adjective phrases using pictures. She instructed her students to examine the images to determine the appropriate descriptor carefully. When her students had difficulty with the topic in the primary activity, TC2 re-explained and provided further examples TC2 presented the slides, including images of "my teacher, my friends, my headmaster, and chairman".

E2: *“Yes, of course, instructional media is important. Teachers, for example, might draw students’ attention by using different kinds of cards, photos, cartoons, charts, and other visual aids. So, students will be more focused on learning, and they will be more concentrated on learning.”* (TC2).

In the first observation, TC3 used maquettes to teach nouns. TC3 presented the media for the students in the opening activity. TC3 divided the students to work in groups. TC3 asked the students to search for other vocabulary for animals, and students could find them in the dictionary. In the second observation, TC3 presented the media for students in the opening activity. Finally, TC3 taught about adjectives and employed maquette. TC3 instructed the student to write a simple sentence that describes the animals in the maquette.

E3: *“I asked students to write simple sentences that describe the animals in the maquette. There are various media today to support learning; we can search on social media or the internet. Also, there are a lot of applications for language learning on the internet.”* (TC3).

For example, during the second observation, TC3 stated that we could bring the city of Mecca to the classroom but we could use the media and bring Mecca for real to the classroom by showing the video from YouTube. It is helpful in everything they will learn. It will motivate the student to achieve the learning objective, attracting their full focus and attention as they become more attractive and livelier. Meanwhile, in the first observation, TC4 taught greeting with pictures, pictures from textbooks, audio, and video. In the opening activity, she showed the picture to the students, then she played the audio and video to give a brief example of greeting. In the second observation, TC4 taught about “Introduce Myself”.

E4: *“I played the audio and video to give a detailed explanation of how to do greeting to my students. In the second meeting, I used the picture in textbooks, and pictures from the laptop that were projected by an LCD projector to explain the structure and information of the name card.”* (TC4).

TC4 gave an exercise to the students where the students were asked to work in pairs in the first observation. TC4 also utilized pictures in textbooks, pictures of name cards, a laptop and a projector to show the picture as the instructional media. In addition, TC4 showed the students an example of a name card with a photo and personal information for the students. Every pair practiced the conversation of greeting after being treated by the instructional media. In the second observation, TC4 asked students to make their name cards by using paper or they could reuse any available paper. The teacher instructed them to make named cards, stick their photos, and write their names, emails, place/date of births, and name of schools.

In an almost similar way, TC5 used pictures, a dictionary, and a textbook to teach procedure text in the first observation. TC5 showed the picture of how to do something related to the procedure text. Meanwhile, TC5 also used realia to teach procedure text under the theme “How to make your drink” in the second observation. Students brought the tools to make their favorite drink and TC5 checked the tools and every group of students presented their media one by one.

E5: *“I explained the procedure text by using the picture to support the learning process. Then, I also instructed the students to search the meaning of difficult words in the dictionary.”* (TC5).

In addition to using the dictionary, TC5 also incorporated a textbook to stimulate students’ ideas about the topic of procedure text with various options. TC5 did not explain the material by using media in the second observation, as the learning process and objective were instilled by having students project in making their favorite drink. Students were asked to bring anything they needed to make their favorite drink. Then, they worked in group and were given time to do presentations on their favorite drink one by one in front of the classroom. TC5 instructed the students in groups to make their favorite drink by using the realia (blender, glass, spoon, and other required equipment). Furthermore, students in groups presented the procedure while making their favorite drinks and the ingredients used.

In the first observation, TC6 introduced the topic of learning by applying the spinning wheel. Furthermore, she presented the spinning wheel for students as the main activity. She virtually did not use the media to explain the learning material. Students were allowed to play the spinning wheel game in the classroom. The game focused on questions and answers about the introduction in English. During the second observation, she used pictures, a laptop, and a projector that had previously been shown to the students to teach family member.

E6: *“I used pictures, a laptop and a projector to teach about family members. Students must identify the family member using the family tree provided to them. Then, I posted a question-and-answer session with students on the topic.”* (TC6).

3.1.2. Beliefs on utilizing instructional media to teach English in the classroom

The interviews revealed that all teacher participants believed that using engaging instructional materials in the classroom when teaching and studying English boosted students' attention. They believed by incorporating instructional media, they could capture students' attention and help them to focus on their studies.

E7: *“Using media for student learning creates a more enjoyable classroom environment. By using media, we can help student in learning. They pay more attention, and when they see the media, the student's attention focuses on the media.”* (TC3).

In addition to gaining students' attention and focus, instructional media can also help student understand more about what they are learning. They believed that using instructional media to achieve the learning objective could be both effective and efficient. TC2 further commented that instructional media could help teachers achieve their teaching and learning objectives:

E8: *“Media can help teachers connect the students' prior knowledge to learning objectives. For instance, when teaching the past tense, I show them pictures depicting various people's past activities.”* (TC2).

The results revealed that the teachers in these schools had favorable attitudes regarding instructional media. They believed incorporating instructional material into the teaching process would benefit the teachers. Additionally, the participants acknowledged that teachers should work on instructional media to make complex content more accessible to students. Furthermore, as they had said, could enhance students' interest in the learning process:

E9: *“Media usage depends on the content; nevertheless, instructional media is preferable because it can help students be more engaged in the learning process.”* (TC2).

Before using instructional media, teachers must make decisions on which instructional media to use. TC2 believed that instructional media should be selected depending on the curriculum and subject. TC2 also stated that selecting instructional material is influenced by the learning style of the students:

E10: *“It is sometimes dependent on the learning characteristics of the students. If the students prefer pictures, then I will use videos. If the students prefer audio, then I will use a radio, tape recorder, or my own voice.”* (TC2).

However, TC6 urged that selecting proper media in teaching is not only based on students' learning style, but also determined by the lesson plan or the material required in the syllabus.

E11: *“The way I choose the media is based on the material listed on the lesson plan. Like what is the material I have to teach this time, and then I have to select the proper media for teaching my students.”* (TC6).

Another aspect of the teachers' belief is that they could teach better if they employed instructional media. From the interviews, they claimed that teaching become more manageable when instructional media was practical and fascinating:

E12: *“Without the use of media, teaching and learning become more difficult and time-consuming. The use of media, on the other hand, will make the teaching and learning process more practical and entertaining.”* (TC1).

Several factors also influence their decision when the teachers chose instructional media. From the interviews, it was revealed that the influences were the students' motivation and interest. TC1 reported that:

E13: *“The first factor that influenced my decision to use media was when observing my students lack of motivation to learn English. When I asked why, they said that it was because English is a*

tricky subject. This means that we, as teachers, must devise effective techniques to ensure that our teaching is more attractive and the use of media is one of the strategies.” (TC1).

Furthermore, there are various modifications that teachers must deal with when employing instructional media. Some factors have influenced the changes. According to TC1, students’ feedback, attending seminars or workshops, and self-discovery are all-important:

E15: “Instructional media should be updated based on students’ needs. From students’ feedback, I have changed the media for my teaching to accommodate my students better. When I attend a seminar or workshop or update my instructional media, I gain deeper information. From self-discovery, I look through some media and find something new, then I choose it.” (TC1).

3.2. Discussion

Based on data analysis from interviews with the teachers, we discovered that the teachers used pictures, whiteboards, and flashcards to teach English. Similarly, According to Smaldino *et al.* [36], photographs are regularly employed instructional media in classrooms to help learning process. Pictures or graphic elements are a more tangible way of communicating a concept [37]. TC1, TC4 and TC5 first showed it to the students in the opening and main activities for each of their lessons. TC1 demonstrated how to use pictures and illustrations to highlight verbal and nominal sentences, as well as past verbs. On the other hand, TC4 showed the picture to the students to give a brief example of a greeting in English and TC5 taught the procedure text using the picture and name card before using realia to teach students “how to make your drink”. In addition, when explaining the lesson to the students, TC1 used a whiteboard to write the material about simple past tense. The whiteboard and flashcards are two examples of among the visual media that can draw students’ attention in the class and help them to focus on the lesson. Given the rapid development of digital services in education, the uses of e-flashcards can be an interactive option for students [38]. The following activity (exercise) was designed to determine if students had grasped the subject delivered through these instructional media [39].

Meanwhile, pictures, LCD projectors, a laptop, and the students themselves were used as the teaching media by TC2 and TC6. In the first meeting, TC1 used pictures to teach noun phrases and TC6 taught the family tree diagram by using pictures, the laptop and the projector in the second meeting. In the primary activity, TC2 requested students to create noun phrases using the pictures in each group. Then when students struggled to develop a concept, the teacher presented an example and instructed them to examine the picture more closely to construct a noun phrase. In addition, TC2 and TC6 began by preparing the material for use in the classroom before beginning to exhibit visuals with an LCD projector and a laptop. They then started to explain, and provide examples. They also used her students as an instructional medium to help them better understand the materials [40]. This process is deemed as one of the appropriate resources in the classroom because the samples taken to explain the lesson are the students themselves. The students can learn more effectively when they directly involved in the process [41].

In terms of the teachers’ belief toward instructional media, all teachers believed that instructional media helped learners become more enthusiastic about learning English. As a result, TC1 concluded that when she used instructional material, she can effectively teach. TC2 claimed that the use of instructional media in the classroom is situational because different lessons necessitate different types of instructional media. As a result, TC1 and TC2 recommended that teachers should employ instructional media to enhance the learning process and choose media that is relevant to the content of the lesson. Using instructional material to teach English will help students in comprehension. Moreover, both TC1 and TC2 agreed that students’ motivation and interest influenced their instructional material usage. Likewise, Chamorro and Rey [19] agreed that technology is an effective medium of learning to increase students’ motivation. They also agreed, as informed by TC6, that teachers believe that technology (i.e., instructional media) as well as the use of online learning resources can help them achieve successful language learning outcomes. Finally, all teachers believed that using instructional media would assist achieve their teaching and learning goals.

According to the responses from TC1, TC2, TC3 and TC6, the teachers’ decisions to use instructional media in the teaching and learning process were influenced by a lack of student motivation and a change in curriculum. Using instructional media, according to TC1, simplified difficult lessons because it was a good way to make the class more entertaining, whilst TC3 expected that using instructional media could help boost students’ motivation and encourages them to provide learning feedbacks, which is very important for teachers. Modifying the curriculum, on the other hand, required TC2 to use media to achieve the curriculum’s goals. Furthermore, feedback from students, attendance in seminars or workshops, self-discovery, and the new curriculum influenced the teachers’ decision to use instructional media. These factors also shaped their beliefs on the use of instructional media in teaching.

According to Richards *et al.* [42], teachers and students should collaborate in the classroom and teachers should know their students, which serves as an immense basis for students' development. Likewise, attending seminars or workshops gave teachers with novel ideas because they gained more knowledge particularly about instructional media from the events. Grip and Pleijers [43] also noted that the attendance at workshops and conferences plays a significant role to teachers because it allows them to stay up to date on external advancements in their profession. As a result, they encourage teachers to apply what they have learned from the events in their classrooms, particularly when it comes to using instructional media. Furthermore, TC1 believed that self-discovery had altered the instructional media in her classroom; she strove to find the media on her own as authentic materials for her teaching, such as in newspapers or on the internet. Teachers' self-confidence and self-actualization, as well as the acquisition of skills and information, are all enhanced by the use of instructional media [44]. The last was the new curriculum and lesson plan which introduced TC1 and TC6 to new insights into instructional media. It is exemplified by Eshetu's work [45], who stated that education is a dynamic process that is constantly changing due to new curriculum content, teaching-learning techniques, and instructional media technology.

4. CONCLUSION

In this study, teachers have demonstrated the use of instructional media and how to prepare it in the classroom before delivering the content. Finally, they requested students to complete some activities based on instructional media material. It benefits students' comprehension of the subject matter and increases their interest in learning. Teachers believe that using instructional material to teach English is advantageous. They believed that instructional media was important and helpful in teaching and learning process. Students' motivation and interest in learning are increased when instructional media is used. It also assists and supports teachers during the teaching process, allowing them to achieve their learning and teaching objectives. As a result, students will have an easier time comprehending the information. Teachers thus select the instructional media based on the topic. Some of the variables that can influence teachers' media selection include students' feedback, self-discovery, attendance at a seminar/workshop/conference, and a new curriculum. Furthermore, the participants in this study were only six teachers, and they were only observed twice, resulting in restricted data for this study. Therefore, future research should include more participants and observation sessions to uncover potentially more comprehensive and contextual accounts of teacher practice and belief regarding the use of instructional media in EFL classrooms.

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